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STUDY OF THE COMPOSITION OF WASTEWATER FROM A DAIRY PLANT

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Annotation. *This article provides an analysis of literary sources, a study of the process of purification of wastewater from the Samarkand small-scale industrial complex from organic pollution and the specific norms of wastewater disposal at a dairy enterprise, that is, in m³ for processed milk. In addition, the need for oxygen for the oxidation of organic substances was determined depending on the composition of milk and the composition of the waste water of a dairy plant.*

Key words: *Wastewater, dairy plant, concentration, purification, water disposal, composition, raw materials, products, consumption, pollution, oxidation, organic matter, suspended matter.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье приведены анализ литературных источников исследование процесса очистки сточных вод Самаркандского маломолочного комбината от органических загрязнений и определены удельные нормы водоотведения на предприятие молочной промышленности, ту есть в м³ на перерабатываемого молоко. Кроме того определены потребность в кислороде на окисление органических веществ в зависимости от состава молоко и состав сточных вод молочного комбината.*

Ключевое слова: *Сточные воды, молочный комбинат, концентрация, очистка, водоотведения, состав, сырьё, продукция, расход, загрязнений, окисление, органических веществ, взвешенные вещества.*

Introduction

Wastewater from dairy industry enterprises is classified as highly concentrated in terms of organic pollutants. Enterprises are usually located in populated areas and wastewater from these enterprises is received in municipal sewers. In accordance with existing regulations, they must be subjected to local (preliminary) treatment on the territory of the enterprise. As a rule, treatment is reduced to reducing the concentration of suspended solids and fats. This ensures protection of sewer networks from blockages and the possibility of extracting valuable substances from wastewater for disposal, such as fats, protein substances, as well as pollutants that complicate subsequent biological treatment of the general discharge of the enterprise and the populated area.

If the enterprise is located outside the populated area, then an independent biological wastewater treatment plant belonging to the enterprise is required. At enterprises, drinking water is used for technological and domestic purposes, contaminated water is removed to the sewerage system and then subjected to appropriate treatment, after which it is discharged either into the city sewerage network or into a reservoir. Circulating systems at food enterprises are arranged only for cooling compressors of refrigeration machines and other units. Thus, the task of designing sewerage and treatment facilities for meat-packing plants and milk processing plants in various conditions of their deployment in relation to populated areas arises. The main goal of the economic reforms carried out in the country is the most complete satisfaction of the material and spiritual needs of people. During the period of reforms, putting forward a broad program of social development of the country and increasing the people's well-being, the task of improving the supply of food to the population was put in the foreground. The reform program provides for the wide use of the potential of agriculture in our country and all sectors of the agro-industrial complex. [1,4]

In order to significantly increase food production, measures have been planned to increase the volume of milk processing, improve the range and enhance the quality of dairy products. The implementation of these measures is associated with the implementation of the tasks of the agro-industrial complex and the technical re-equipment of the food industry, including the dairy industry.

During the technical re-equipment of the dairy industry, it is envisaged to use high-performance

technological equipment, manufacture sets of machines, devices and flow technological lines that ensure increased milk productivity, master new technological equipment and automated lines for bottling milk and equipment for packaging dairy products.

Dairy industry enterprises have modern, highly productive equipment, including flow-mechanized and automated lines. The production of new types of whole milk products, cheeses, ice cream, canned milk, butter, baby food products, whole milk substitutes for young farm animals has been mastered. Recently, special attention has been focused on the complex processing of milk and its rational use by processing skim milk, buttermilk and whey into various food products. Specific wastewater consumption. Specific water consumption and water disposal rates for dairy industry enterprises of various profiles and productivity are given in Table 1. The rates given in Table 1 are valid for enterprises with modern equipment and the highest possible degree of repeated and recycled use of water in production. Actual specific consumption rates of consumed water and discharged wastewater at dairy plants where there is no strict control over water consumption and an insufficient degree of repeated and recycled use often exceed the standard values. Wastewater discharge unevenness coefficients fluctuate depending on the capacity of the enterprise within the range of 1.4-2.

Composition of wastewater. Industrial polluted wastewater at dairy plants is formed mainly during the process of washing equipment, containers, and during cleaning of production facilities. These wastewaters are polluted by losses of milk and dairy products, production waste, reagents used in cleaning equipment, and impurities washed off the surfaces of containers, floors, transport, etc. In order to reduce the amount of pollutants discharged by the plant with wastewater, the technological process must include measures to reduce the loss of raw materials and products, collection and disposal of whey (by thickening, drying, processing into milk sugar or selling as feed), collection and separation of the first portions of water obtained from rinsing technological equipment for the production of high-fat products, circulation and regeneration of cleaning solutions, etc. The amount of pollutants in wastewaters can be determined on the basis of the standards for the loss of raw materials, dairy products and specific wastewater consumption (see Table 1).

Table 1.

**Specific standards of water consumption and water disposal at the Samarkand Dairy Plant
(in m³ per 1 ton of processed milk)**

Samarkand dairy plant	Specific consumption of water consumed			Specific wastewater consumption			Irrecoverable consideration and losses of water
	Recyclable, reusable	Fresh from the source		total	industrial	domestic	
		For production needs	For household needs				
Milk collection points and separator departments	0	2,2	0,1	2	1,9	0,1	0,3
City dairy plants with a capacity of, tons per day							
up to 50	30	6,3	0,7	5,6	4,9	0,7	1,4
over 50 up to 200	30,5	5,8	0,7	5,2	4,5	0,7	1,3
condensed milk products plants with capacity, tubes per shift							
up to 60 (180 tons of milk per day)	25	5,2	0,3	4,4	4,1	0,3	1,1
over 60 (180 tons of milk per day)	25,5	4,7	0,2	4	3,7	0,3	1
dry milk product plants (whole and skim milk,							

DMP), butter factories with drying shops, capacity, tons per day							
up to 300	20	4,7	0,3	4	3,7	0,3	1
Milk processing plants for baby products Butter factories with a capacity of t per day	20	3,3	0,2	3	2,8	0,2	0,5
up to 50	21	2,8	0,2	2,6	2,4	0,2	0,4
over 50 up to 200	21,5	2,3	0,2	2,1	1,9	0,2	0,4
Butter and cheese factories with capacity, tons per day	20	4,6 4,2	0,4	4,3	3,9	0,4	0,7
up to 50	20,5		0,3	3,8	3,5	0,3	0,7
over 50 up to 200		6,5 5,6					
Cheese factories with capacity, tons per day	19		0,5				1 1
up to 50	19,5		0,4	6	5,5	0,5	
over 50 up to 200				5 4,3	4,6	0,4	

The concentration of wastewater contaminants is calculated using the formula

$$C=(\Pi_1C_1+\Pi_2C_2+\dots+\Pi_nC_n)/(N_1+N_2+\dots+N_n), (1)$$

where C is the concentration of wastewater contaminants, g/m³; Π_1, Π_2, Π_n are the losses of milk and dairy products in various technological production cycles, fractions of a unit; C_1C_2, C_n is the specific amount of contaminants per unit of milk and dairy product losses, g/t; $N_1; N_2; N_n$ is the specific consumption of wastewater per unit of milk and dairy products, m³/t.

The amount of contaminants according to COD* and BOD_{poly} of milk and dairy products is determined using Table 2. Knowing the losses of milk and dairy products at the enterprise and using the data in Table 2, the concentration of these contaminants in wastewater can be determined using the formula.

Table 2.
Oxygen requirement for oxidation of organic substances depending on the composition of milk and dairy products

Product	Dry matter %	Fat, %	Protein, %	Lactose, %	COD, kg/t	BOD _{total} , kg/t
Whole milk	11,5-12,5	3-4	3,3	4,8	192,9-218,6	135,5-156,2
skim	8,3-8,47	0,02-0,06	3,3	4,7-4,9	112-115,3	72,4-75,1
Buttermilk	7,7-8,0	0,4-0,86	1	4,5-4,7	72-77	51,6-55,9
Whey	6-6,2	0,1-0,2	1	4,5-4,7	72-77	51,6-55,9
Cream	40,4-43	33,35	2	4,7-3	871-936,5	695-747

When calculating the concentrations of wastewater contaminants using the formula, additional contaminants from used cleaning solutions entering the sewer system, product additives, etc. should be taken into account. Actual concentrations of wastewater contaminants from dairy industry enterprises vary widely and depend on the profile and capacity of the enterprise, production technology, type of equipment used, degree of reuse and recycling of uncontaminated wastewater, losses of raw materials, disposal of production waste, etc. The obtained data on the composition of wastewater from dairy industry enterprises of various profiles are presented in Table 3. The temperature of wastewater from dairy industry enterprises varies from 16 to 33° C. The high discharge temperature is due to the use of hot water for washing equipment and cleaning premises. The average monthly temperature of wastewater discharged by dairy plants is 17-18° C in winter and 22-25° C in summer. The pH value of wastewater is largely determined by the production technology and the range of products manufactured.

For industries not associated with lactic acid fermentation processes, the pH of the discharge is [2.3].

Table 3.

Composition of wastewater from dairy industry enterprises

Enterprises	Suspended solids, mg/l	COD, (mg/l)	BOD _{total} , mg/l	Fats, mg/l	Chlorides, mg/l	Total nitrogen, mg/l	Phosphorus, mg/l	pH
City Dairy Plants	350	1400	1200	До 100	150	60	8	6,5-5,5
Dry and Condensed Milk Plants	350	1200	100	До 100	150	50	7	6,8-7,4
Cheese Plants	600	3000	2400	До 100	200	90	16	6,2-7

close to neutral (6.8-7.4 for dairy canning plants, butter factories). At cheese factories, city dairies and other enterprises producing cottage cheese and fermented milk products, a certain amount of whey is discharged into the sewerage system, which causes a decrease in the pH of the wastewater to 6.2. Fluctuations in the pH of the discharge are also often caused by the discharge of acid-containing and alkaline reagents used in cleaning equipment into the sewerage system. A sharp short-term increase in the pH of the total discharge to 10-10.5 can be explained by the salvo discharge of alkaline cleaning solutions, which are mainly used in dairies. Long-term presence of wastewater in anaerobic conditions (in the sewer network, settling tanks) causes the liquid to sour as a result of lactic acid fermentation and leads to a decrease in pH. Suspended solids in wastewater from dairy plants are represented by particles of solid milk processing products (pieces of cottage cheese, milk films, cheese grains, etc.) and other impurities (soil, sand) that enter the sewerage system during the washing of technological equipment, containers, and premises. The main part of the suspended solids (up to 90%) is organic matter, usually of protein origin. The concentration of suspended solids varies widely depending on the technological production cycle. Fluctuations in the concentration of suspended solids in the wastewater of dairy plants are also observed by the hours of the day; The largest amount of suspended matter enters during the initial period of equipment washing. The values of COD and BOD of wastewater from dairy plants also vary widely and, on average, are 1400 and 1200 mg/l for municipal dairy plants; for cheese factories - 3000 and 2400 mg/l. It has been established that there is a direct relationship between the COD and BOD_{full} (Fig. 1) indicators for wastewater from dairy plants: $BOD_{full} = (0.80-0.84) COD$. Using this ratio, based on the COD value (the analytical determination of which takes 2-3 hours), one can approximately calculate the BOD_{full} of wastewater from a dairy processing plant of any profile, which significantly simplifies the analysis of the composition of wastewater and monitoring the operation of treatment facilities. It should be borne in mind that there is no clear relationship between BOD₅ and BOD_{total}, as well as between BOD_z and COD, therefore, the BOD_v value for wastewater from dairy plants is not an objective indicator of wastewater pollution. The fat content in wastewater from dairy enterprises is determined mainly by the range of products manufactured and the production technology. Depending on these factors, not only the concentration of fats in wastewater changes, but also the type of these pollutants. Wastewater from whole milk production contains fats in the same form as natural milk, since milk losses are the main pollution of these effluents. Milk fats are tiny balls surrounded by a hydrated protein shell, which float extremely slowly during wastewater settling. In the production of high-fat products (cream, sour cream, butter), large fat globules are extracted from milk, they stick together and become larger, and the protein shell is destroyed. Therefore, the fatty impurities contained in the wastewater of such industries differ significantly in type and concentration from similar pollutants in the wastewater of other dairies. The separation of fatty impurities from wastewater from the production of high-fat products, for example, by settling the liquid, occurs much faster and more effectively than from wastewater from other industries. During sanitary analysis of wastewater, the

content of fats and fat-like substances extracted with ether or chloroform is determined. The concentration of extractable substances in wastewater from factories and workshops specializing in the production of high-fat products is 200-400 mg/l, in wastewater from other types of production it usually does not exceed 100 mg/l. In wastewater from dairy plants, nitrogen is contained mainly in the form of amino groups of protein compounds. In small quantities, nitrogen from ammonium salts from ammonia compressors also enters the runoff. The content of total nitrogen in wastewater from city dairies, milk canning plants, and butter factories is 50-60 mg/l, or 4.2-6% of BOD; cheese factories - 90 mg/l, or 3.7% of BOD. The concentration of phosphorus is 0.6-0.7% of BOD. The concentrations of nitrogen and phosphorus salts are sufficient for the normal course of the process of biological treatment of wastewater from dairy industry enterprises and the reproduction of bacteria involved in the oxidation of pollutants in these effluents. During biological treatment of wastewater from cheese factories, nitrification processes are less intensive than during the treatment of effluents from other dairy industry enterprises, due to the lower content of nitrogen salts in relation to the BOD.

Fig. 1. Relationship between BOD_{total} and COD of wastewater from dairy industry enterprises

Conclusions:

The analysis of literary sources in the study of the process of cleaning wastewater from organic pollutants of a dairy plant is presented, specific standards of water consumption and water disposal at the Samarkand Dairy Plant are determined, i.e. in m³ per 1 m of processed milk. The organic substances depending on the composition of milk and the composition of wastewater at the Samarkand Dairy Plant are determined. In addition, it is established that between the indicators COD_{total} and BOD_{total}, there is a direct relationship $BOD_{total} = (0.8 \div 0.82) HP$.

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